

PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDES. A CONTRIBUTION TO THE
STUDY OF THE TRIAD .N.C.S. PART XII. PHENYL-
CYANAMIDE, ITS PROPERTIES AND DERIVATIVES.
THE PHENYLHYDRAZINE α -CARBOXYLIC ACID.

BY RAMCHANDRA SAHASRABUDHEY AND HANS KRALL.

Phenylcyanamide has been obtained by the desulphurisation of phenylthiocarbamide by copper acetate in alkaline or neutral medium. The properties of phenylcyanamide and of its derivatives have been investigated and the isolation of the hydrochloride of phenylhydrazine- α -carboxylic acid is described.

The close relationship of phenylcyanamide with phenylthiocarbamide necessitated an investigation of its properties because it appears not to have been systematically studied and the data are incomplete and misleading. The easiest method of its preparation is by desulphurisation of phenylthiocarbamide in an alkaline medium. Lead acetate, lead oxide and benzyl chloride were used for this purpose by the earlier workers (Rathke, *Ber.*, 1879, 12, 772; Feuerlein, *ibid.*, p. 1602; Hofmann, *Ber.*, 1885, 18, 3217; Berger, *Monatsh.*, 1884, 8, 317; Traube and Wedelstadt, *Ber.*, 1900, 33, 1383; Fromm, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 1302). We have found copper acetate to act in an analogous manner. In $N/2$ alkaline medium the yields are 75 and 65% respectively for lead and copper acetate. An excess of copper acetate or lead acetate does not affect the yield but an increase in the alkalinity of the medium from $N/2$ to $2N$ concentration increases the yield by about 10%. The action of copper acetate is remarkable in that it can also desulphurise phenylthiocarbamide in an aqueous medium; the yield of phenylcyanamide is, however, poor.

Hofmann and Feuerlein (*loc. cit.*) assigned the compositions $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CN}\cdot\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $(\text{NH}:\text{C}:\text{NPh})_2\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ respectively to the hydrates of the compound. Our results, however, show that the compound is a cyanamide and not carbodiimide and that different hydrates are formed at different temperatures.

The hydrates of phenylcyanamide. At about 30° monohydrate is chiefly formed while at 0° to 15° trihydrate with possibly smaller quantities of a still higher hydrate is the chief product. These various hydrates lose water of crystallisation spontaneously at ordinary temperatures or on warming and it is probably due to this property that Hofmann and Feuerlein assigned the above formulae. When dehydrated in a vacuum desiccator over

concentrated sulphuric acid or otherwise (*vide infra*) they are converted into anhydrous phenylcyanamide, which is a thick viscous liquid.

Polymerisation. Phenylcyanamide in absence of a solvent undergoes quick polymerisation, triphenylisomelamine (Hofmann, *loc. cit.*) being exclusively formed. The crystals of the hydrate are completely changed when heated on a water-bath for half an hour. At ordinary temperatures the hydrate takes about one week, whilst the anhydrous product completely polymerises within 48 hours. The kinetics of polymerisation could not be studied owing to difficulties in the estimation of the compound in aqueous solutions.

Phenylcyanamide is very soluble in ether and an ethereal solution, dehydrated over sodium sulphate, keeps unchanged for long periods. In acetone also it is easily soluble and this solution has good keeping qualities but a benzene solution throws down the insoluble triphenylisomelamine in a comparatively short time.

Estimation. Conditions for the estimation of phenylcyanamide in aqueous solution have been ascertained. It is precipitated as silver salt with an excess of silver nitrate, the excess being then volumetrically estimated.

Reduction of phenylcyanamide. Phenylcyanamide is reluctant to undergo reduction. Ammonia and aniline were detected when reduced with zinc and sodium hydroxide. It may be recalled that all attempts to reduce phenylthiocarbamide without breaking it down have failed.

Action of metallic sodium on anhydrous phenylcyanamide. A sodium derivative with the composition $C_7H_5N_2Na$ is obtained. When heated it melts above 300° and then burns off leaving a residue of sodium cyanide. The structure of the sodium salt is PhN^+NaCN^- as suggested by the following reaction

Calcium chloride in ethereal solution probably throws down the calcium salt but this has not been examined. Discussion of the bearing of these results on the problem of constitution of phenylthiocarbamide is postponed pending the completion of further investigations, now in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Phenylcyanamide.—Phenylthiocarbamide (5 g.) was dissolved in about 100 c.c. of boiling water and to this were added the requisite quantities of alkali and the lead or copper acetates, also in boiling hot solution. The quantity of alkali was so taken as to completely cover the

neutralisation of the acetic acid of the salt added with enough excess to render the medium alkaline to the desired concentration. The total bulk of the mixture varied between 130 and 150 c.c. Immediately on addition of the lead or copper salt a black precipitate came down. The mixture was boiled for 10 minutes, then cooled and filtered. The filtrate was surrounded with ice and phenylcyanamide precipitated with a slight excess of strong acetic acid.

Determination of the Water of Hydration.

(i) Phenylcyanamide was dissolved in hot water and the crystals that came down at about 30° collected and dried. Known weights of these were allowed to polymerise at ordinary temperatures as also by heating on a water-bath till the m.p. and weight were constant. Water of hydration is lost in this process. In various experiments 17.5 to 22.0 g. of water were found to have combined with every 118 g. of PhNH·CN indicating that at about 30° monohydrate is chiefly obtained.

(ii) In another set of experiments anhydrous phenylcyanamide was rehydrated with ice-cold water. These samples when dehydrated were found to contain about 3 moles of water for every mole of PhNH·CN. In one experiment as many as 4 moles of water were found.

(iii) Measurements of heats of hydration were conducted at 10°, 15° and 20° but almost constant values were obtained.

Polymerisation of Phenylcyanamide.

When anhydrous phenylcyanamide or the hydrate was allowed to stand at ordinary temperatures or warmed triphenylisomelamine, crystallisable from dilute alcohol, was obtained, m.p. 185°. (Found : N, 23.4. Calc. for triphenylisomelamine : N, 23.7 per cent).

A benzene solution also deposited triphenylisomelamine. Aqueous solution of phenylcyanamide also deposits the crystals of triphenylisomelamine.

Hydrolysis of Phenylcyanamide.

Action of Water and of Aqueous Acids and Alkalis.—Solubility of phenylcyanamide in water is less than 1%. In neutral solutions hydrolysis to phenylurea is not observed but polymerisation to triphenylisomelamine occurs followed by other complicated changes: First into a compound which crystallises from water in long white fibrous crystals, m.p. 209°. This change takes place even at ordinary temperatures and also in alcoholic solutions and is accelerated in a slightly alkaline medium. On prolonged

boiling with water or alkali it redissolves undergoing further chemical changes, probably forming some oxy derivative. Phenylcyanamide is easily soluble in glacial acetic acid and in aqueous solutions of mineral acids. In aqueous acidic solutions there is no evidence of polymerisation but it is quantitatively hydrolysed to phenylcarbamide. The rate of hydrolysis in mineral acid solutions has been found greater than in acetic acid solutions.

Aqueous caustic alkalis and ammonia simply dissolve phenylcyanamide. Evidently the alkaline metal salts are formed in solutions, and even in presence of an excess of alkali it does not undergo any further changes, but can be precipitated by acids in the form of its hydrates.

Solutions of phenylcyanamide in dilute aqueous acetic acid and mineral acids were allowed to stand at ordinary temperatures. Estimations of phenylcyanamide in these were done after every 24 hours. It was found that the strength of mineral acid solutions decreased faster than acetic acid solutions. On evaporating these solutions on a water-bath pure samples of phenylcarbamide were left behind. Triphenylisourelamine could not be detected.

Estimation of Phenylcyanamide.— $M/10$ solution of phenylcyanamide in $N/4$ sodium hydroxide solution was used. The solution was first rendered acidic with known quantities of glacial acetic acid and then silver salt of phenylcyanamide precipitated with an excess of standard silver nitrate solution.

The mixture was allowed to stand for 5 minutes, filtered and the filtrate with the washings estimated for silver nitrate using $N/20$ ammonium thiocyanate by Volhards' method. The effect of dilution was studied by adding distilled water to the phenylcyanamide solution before precipitation. Effect of addition of some mineral acid salts and large excess of silver nitrate was also studied. Phenylcyanamide in pure aqueous or alkaline solutions could be estimated with reasonable accuracy when the strength was below $M/30$ or $M/35$. In pure aqueous medium or in presence of excess of acetic acid (enough to render the solution N to $2N$) it could be precipitated as the silver salt with an excess of aqueous silver nitrate solution, the excess being estimated by Volhards' method. Excess of silver nitrate did not interfere nor did an excess of acetic acid up to a concentration of approximately $3N$. In higher concentrations of acetic acid or in more dilute solutions of phenylcyanamide the precipitation of silver salt was not complete and low values were obtained.

In solutions which did not contain alkali there was no need of addition of acetic acid, while if a large proportion of alkali be present, acetic acid had to be increased proportionately to suppress the hydroxyl ions. Presence of

mineral acids and their salts interfered. The chief limitation of this method, however, is the fact that the transformation products of phenylcyanamide also form insoluble silver salts.

Action of dry HCl gas on Anhydrous Phenylcyanamide.—Dry HCl gas gave a pale brown liquid from an ethereal solution of anhydrous phenylcyanamide. This when immediately treated with water reverted to phenylcyanamide, hydrochloric acid being dissolved away but if warmed on a water-bath for about half an hour it crystallised as white needles, m.p. 118°.

The crystals are hydrolysed to phenylcarbamide liberating free acid on treatment with water. The HCl and $\text{PhNH}\cdot\text{CN}$ are present in 1 : 1 ratio indicating that the crystalline derivative is $\text{PhNH}\cdot\text{CN}\cdot\text{HCl}$, M.W. 153.5.

Action of Concentrated Sulphuric Acid on Anhydrous Phenylcyanamide.—Concentrated sulphuric acid when gradually added to an ethereal anhydrous solution of phenylcyanamide heat was generated and a very viscous, pale brown, clear liquid separated out. This was thoroughly washed with ether and freed from impurity by warming on a water-bath. When treated with water, like the hydrochloride it was hydrolysed to phenylcarbamide and sulphuric acid, the quantities obtained indicating the composition, $\text{PhNH}\cdot\text{CN}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$. The liquid does not show any definite boiling point. When heated at 200° for 4 hours it is transformed into sulphanilic acid as shown by the molecular weight, sulphur content, the bromo derivative and other properties of the product.

Action of Nitrous Acid on Phenylcyanamide.—To 50 c.c. of a 10% ethereal solution of phenylcyanamide were added 9 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. A concentrated aqueous solution of 4.5 g. of sodium nitrite was then gradually run in with constant stirring. When effervescence had ceased the deep yellow compound that had separated was collected, yield 5.5 g. The compound crystallises from 50% alcohol in peg-shaped slender crystals, m.p. 155-56°. [Found : N, 28.2. Calc. for $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{N}(\text{NO})\cdot\text{CN}$: N, 28.5 per cent].

It contains a nitroso group as shown by its reaction with potassium iodide in presence of a mineral acid when iodine is liberated indicating the presence of free nitrous acid. It has, therefore, the composition $\text{PhN}(\text{NO})\text{CN}$. When digested on a water-bath for 3 to 4 hours with an excess of sodium hydroxide solution, ammonia was evolved and bright orange-red needles separated out on concentrating the liquors. This is probably the sodium salt of phenylnitrosocarbanic acid, $\text{PhN}(\text{NO})\cdot\text{COONa}$. It is very explosive. From an aqueous solution of this, silver nitrate precipitates a bright yellow silver salt which also when heated burns with a mild explosion. [Found :

Ag, 39.1; M. W., 277. Ph.N(NO)COOAg requires Ag, 39.5 per cent. M. W., 273].

Hydrochloric acid throws down a very pale yellow compound from the aqueous solutions of the sodium salt. This is probably the free acid. It does not show any definite melting point.

Reduction of the Phenylnitrosocarbamic Acid.—The sodium salt was warmed for a few minutes with an excess of tin and dilute hydrochloric acid, and the clear solution concentrated on a water-bath when a mixture of the crystals of SnCl_2 and the reduction product separated out. They were dissolved in water and tin removed as SnS by passing H_2S . When completely freed of tin salts the residue was crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid (animal charcoal). This is, $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{N}\cdot\text{COOH}$, the hydrochloride of phenylhydrazine- α -carboxylic acid.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
AGRA COLLEGE, AGRA.

Received April 27, 1942.
